

FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: The article analyzes research on the organization of the educational process in preschool education and touches upon its issues in order to further improve this process.

Keywords: preschool education, innovative method, innovative technology, individualization of education, person-centered education, thinking, educational trajectory.

Introduction: Modern education of children from preschool age, active development of them psychically, mentally and socially - is one of the most pressing issues that should be solved in preschool educational organizations today [1].

One of our important tasks is to bring up the young generation growing in our country over the past period as healthy and mature in every way, to introduce effective forms and methods into the educational process and to organize an effective system of preschool education aimed at promoting innovative ideas. At the same time, the analysis carried out shows the need to ensure the coverage of children with preschool education, fill organizations with educational and methodological materials and fiction, attract qualified pedagogical and managerial personnel to the field, and solve the issues of introducing innovative technologies in the educational process. The effective implementation of these tasks places a tremendous responsibility on the part of educators, stylists and psychologists operating in preschool educational organizations [2, 3].

Literature analysis and methodology: Scientific research work of a number of scientists is devoted to the problem of education of children in preschool educational organizations.

For Example, F.R.Kadirova, Sh.Q.Toshpolatova, N.M.Kayumova, M.N.Azamova and Sh.A.Sadigova [4] in her scientific research, the scientific-theoretical foundations of the theory and methodology of preschool education are studied, scientific research methods, stages of preschool pedagogy, biological and social factors affecting the development of children, the main stages of the psychological development of a child in preschool age, didactic principles of Education, pedagogical influence on children, the forms and methods of organizing preschool education and the theoretical foundations of the application of pedagogical technologies in preschool education and education are covered.

Abdullaeva N.Sh., A'zamova M.N., Gulyamov Dj.R., Nurbayev G.M., Khuzhakulov N.T., Rustamova A.E. and others carried out research work on improving preschool education on the basis of a variative approach, improving the system of formation of cooperation skills based on friendly relations in schoolchildren of preparatory groups, the formation and development of pronunciation in teaching a foreign language in preschool children [5-8].

Discussion And Results: The state educational program of a preschool educational institution (below: "MTM state educational program") is a meyoril-legal document developed in accordance with the state requirements for the development of children of the first and preschool age of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in which the goals and objectives of the preschool educational institution, the main ideas of educational activities are expressed, as well as the

Educational activities are carried out on the basis of" state requirements for the development of children of the first and school age of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

In preschool institutions, classes begin from 9.30 in the morning, the duration of which is up to 10-15 minutes in small groups, in large and preparatory groups-no more than 25-30 minutes. Between classes, refreshing, fatigue-taking games are played with children. In each direction, at the end of the month, incarnate - control classes are held with children, and to what extent the children occupy the tasks of the program are analyzed. In the "educational play-exercises"(sensory training), which are included in the schedule of training group 1, it is recommended to widely use one of the modern pedagogical technologies - the methodology of Maria Montessori.

1. in a small group, the training of acquaintance with the surrounding world, distributed from 0.5 - with the training of acquaintance with nature, the training of acquaintance with fiction - with the training of mud, and the training of building-making is replaced by one week of large building equipment, one time with small building equipment.

2. starting from a small group, the schedule alternates from 0.5 with the practice of familiarization with distributed nature - with fiction, and the practice of building - making with the practice of appliqué.

In large-preparatory groups, the building-making training is exchanged for manual labor. The tasks of reading and preparation for literacy include in a small group mainly exercises for the correct pronunciation of sounds.

In medium, large groups, the tasks of training and preparation for literacy are carried out in addition to the tasks of speech training.

- In the preparatory group, on the other hand, a preparatory training is introduced to a separate literate.

- The educator draws up a monthly educational work plan and gives it to the Methodist for approval.

- The monthly work plan book is completed as follows:

- title sheet of the work plan;

- approved weekly training schedule;

- Perspective Plan of a month of training;

- complex of 2 morning badantarbia exercises for every 15 days;

- plan to work with parents;

- in the main part of the plan - the description of daily activities is illuminated. Daily business plan.

- The Daily plan is stated as follows:

- morning hour;

- Training;

- Sayre;

- - 2nd half of the day;
- - Evening walk.
- Daily plan. Morning.
- - Interview (topic;
- - Games (theme;
- - Independent activities;
- - Labor;
- - Work with children individually.
- - Badantarbia Training
- - Training direction, subject and purpose.
- - Necessary equipment and visual aids.
- - Training progress (components)
- Components of training (given as an example)
- - Introduction;
- - Q & A;
- - PHOTO View;
- - Story-making;
- - Game;
- - Generalization;
- - Finish.
- The sequence of ride segments can vary depending on the theme received ride
- - Observation.
- - Action game.
- - Optional games.
- - Labor.
- - Quiet game (you can plan to work individually if there are fewer than 20 children in the group)
- Second half of the day
 - - Individual work.
 - Expressive reading and conversation.
 - Games (Educational, on the table, eventful, optional, staged).
 - Entertainment hours (1-2 times a month.) Evening tour
 - Optional tracking;
 - Optional games;
 - Work with parents.

The following requirements are imposed on the writing of the statement of the Daily plan:

- the main task of pedagogical work, which is done in the morning hour, is to evoke a trigger, cheerful mood in children. In this, the activities of the child will be free, the desire and interest of the child will be relied on, the form and content of the activities will be ensured to be interesting. The educator receives every morning hour on the basis of a primary medical examination of children, conducts an interview with parents, conducts badantarbia exercises.

- The daily activity statement shows that in the morning hour the educator will organize a short conversation with children on the specified topic, the main place will be allocated for children's play activities. It is planned to organize creative games, peaceful Games (build-make, Watch picture books).

- In the plan, the labor activity of children is widely covered. The four tasks of labor education are written in five days. Duty is not scheduled separately for each day. The plan will cover the new content separately if the duty of duty is updated, the duty of duty is complicated or the circumstances change.

- Independent activities of children are not planned, it depends on the interest and mood of the child. Each child can freely choose the center of activity he wants and work there. The educator must monitor the children and, if necessary, provide him with assistance.

- The educator should not forget: not to force the child in the center of activity; to provide an opportunity for the child to operate freely. The main thing is that in the center of activity everything should be interesting for the child.

- For the purpose of training, the educator shows the educational and educational tasks assigned to children, clearly determines the size of the knowledge, skills and qualifications that children should acquire. It is enough to indicate the author of the source, the page of the development, so that the course of the training is not completely written. Then shows the necessary equipment and exhibitions. If there is no methodological manual on which the training development is written, the educator must write the training development.

The following requirements are imposed on the writing of the Daily Plan report:

- The educator does not write a daily report. The children who cannot master the topic mentioned during the training will be marked in the notebook of solo work on the same day when, on what topic, solo work will be carried out with these children. The educator should conduct solo work every morning, on a walk, on the 2nd half of the day with children who have not mastered it.

- The tutor prepares and conducts a control exercise at the end of each month. Analysis of the control exercise is carried out on the last days of the current month. A statement on the training analysis is written, and according to the result of the training, tasks are assigned to each educator.

- Twice during the school year (1st half-year, 2nd half - year), child development indicators are analyzed on the basis of state requirements.

It is necessary that the educator's correct planning of educational work is primarily aimed at organizing and improving the pedagogical process by types of activities.

Analysis of Child Development Indicators:

Based on the state requirements for the development of preschool children: physical development of preschool children, socio-emotional development, preparation for speech, reading and literacy, and the process of cognition, determination of the knowledge, skills and qualifications that should be acquired in the areas of knowledge of the surrounding world and its perception are carried out on the 1st half-year (September, October, November, December),

- The tutor prepares and conducts a control exercise at the end of each month. Analysis of the control exercise is carried out on the last days of the current month. A statement on the training analysis is written, and according to the result of the training, tasks are assigned to each educator.

• Twice during the school year (1st half-year, 2nd half - year), child development indicators are analyzed on the basis of state requirements.

Educators of preschools (MTMS) should prepare separately for such activities, which, in turn, also provides opportunities for expanding the scope of professional interests of educators, that is, their study from reading literature to conducting theoretical psychological and pedagogical and fundamental research. Good scientific and pedagogical training ensures the effectiveness of innovative activities. An educational educator who actively participates in innovative processes regularly becomes a catalyst for self-development and improvement of the preschool education system, that is, it is important in the acceleration of these processes.

Based on the above taxile results, one can conclude that:

1. Objective and subjective factors contribute to the organization of innovative activities of educators in MTM. We can cite to objective factors the new educational policy of the state, fundamental and Applied Research in the field of education, the experience of the educational institution in the direction of innovative activities.

2. And subjective factors will be exemplified by socio-territorial need, the process of development of the activities of the MTM, knowledge, skills and qualifications of educators, the development of scientific potential, the growth of the potential of an educational institution, changes in managerial characteristics.

Conclusions And Suggestions: Thus, one of the solutions to the problem of improving the educational process in preschool educational organizations is, first of all, the introduction into practice of innovative methods of teaching and training - the application of innovative technologies of training aimed at the person who is brought up in the educational process in the educational process.

Education of children in preschool educational organizations on the basis of interactive didactic games and materials - allows the organization of education aimed at the personality of the child. Such educational activities arouse great interest in children, during the game logical and creative thinking develops without excessive tension, skills for social activity and compliance with moral standards are brought up, their perception of the natural and social environment is regulated, and the correct formation of concepts is ensured. To do this, the educator will have to focus on what they themselves can do in the education of preschool children not independently, but with the help and guidance of adults

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